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A literature review on the Portuguese emigration literature and acculturation

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Abstract

This article discusses a statistical review done on the Observatório da Emigração's database, which has references about the Portuguese emigration literature. The literature review aimed to fulfill two goals, i.e., to get a deeper comprehension about the appraisals regarding cultural change, and to single out the Portuguese emigration literature, according to the acculturation models, updating it. The assimilation model is pervasive in the Portuguese literature. The multicultural and the fusion models are scarce. The present article is proposing that the multicultural model should be taken into account, in order to approach the maintenance of the Portuguese culture. The fusion model should also be taken into account, because emigrants can reinterpret the Portuguese and the host cultures. Acculturation is mainly a learning process, and it causes cultural changes, due to the fusion of cultures.

Keywords: acculturation, emigration, fusion, equivalence, multicultural

Palavras-chave: aculturação, emigração, fusão, equivalência, multicultural

Introduction

The current paper discusses a literature review done on the *Observatório da Emigração's* (<http://observatorioemigracao.pt>) database, which has references about the Portuguese emigration. The *Observatório da Emigração* was just established in 2008 and started to work in 2009 and it is the most extensive and robust database about the Portuguese emigration phenomenon. Portugal has a long past on the emigration topic. On the Portuguese culture, emigration is older than the immigration topic. The emigration phenomenon started with the independence of Brazil in 1822, and the immigration topic started barely in 1974, after the decolonization. Usually, the acculturation literature approaches immigrants, and it rarely approaches emigrants. Hence, this paper offers an unusual point of view, because Portugal is shaped by emigration flows.

In recent decades the importance of intercultural relationships has increased. On one hand, the acculturation concept is a resource to understand the intercultural relationships (Leal, 2011), on the other hand, the Portuguese emigration phenomenon allows to check out how the acculturation concept has evolved in the Portuguese culture. The literature of social representations (Araújo and Maeso, 2010) reports how cultural borders can influence the reactions regarding cultural changes. This article states that the Portuguese history is a resource to understand the reactions regarding migrations (Feldman-Bianco, 2007) and in particular it is a resource to understand acculturation.

On the present article, the acculturation phenomenon is perceived as contextualized, because the cultural background shapes the reactions towards cultural changes. The cultural background also shapes the theoretical rationales. Consequently, given that the acculturation phenomenon was developed in the United States and especially in Canada, it is required to contextualize the concept towards the Portuguese culture.

1. Acculturation definition and models

The acculturation definition is important to set out the limits of the research, and also to understand the outcomes of the review. Acculturation is defined by its fundamental dimensions: intercultural contact, reciprocal interaction among different cultures (Redfield,

Linton and Herskovits, 1936), learning a second culture (Powell, 1880) and cultural changes at individual and collective levels (Malinowski, 1958). On the acculturation definition, it is important to consider that cultural changes can reshape the cultural legacy (Barth, 1969), because acculturation is a dynamic process of cultural creation (Boas, 1982). Acculturation is also ruled by strong motivations (Castro, 2014a; Rudmin, 2009; Rudmin, Wang and Castro, 2016).

The word 'acculturation' was coined by Powell (1880), and it was related to learning a second culture. Previously, the cultural exchanges were approached through the concept of cultural diffusion, yet diffusion does not imply interaction. The acculturation concept was influenced by its historical evolution, and it got an ambiguous meaning linked to the colonial past (Rudmin, Wang and Castro, 2016). However, the concept has unique features as an analytical tool (Leal, 2011). On the current article acculturation will be approached mainly as learning (Castro, 2016a and 2006b) and the main features from the acculturation models will be described. However, it is necessary to cast light into a theoretical detail. The words 'majority' and 'minority' are applied on the current paper, because they are employed on the pervasive Anglo-Saxon literature. It is necessary to standardize the concepts at the international stage, regardless that they should be targets of critical points of view. Hence, the accurate words would be the dominant cultural group and the dominated cultural group.

Arends-Tóth and Van de Vijver (2006) pointed out to the existence of three acculturation models: assimilation, multicultural, and fusion. Castro (2012, 2014a and 2014b) added the intercultural model, which corresponds to the Francophone cultural background (Taylor, 2012). According to Castro (2014a, 2014b and 2015), on the assimilation model, the minority is expected to disappear, after having adapted completely the dominant culture. The mutual learning will not be reported on the expected outcome, i.e., assimilation. The European policies of cultural uniformity on the 19th century, and also the Chicago School conceptualization (Park, 1928) are examples of the model.

On the multicultural model, the minority is expected to adapt the dominant culture, maintaining at the same time its culture (Berry, 2001). On the multicultural model, only the minority learns the majority culture, and both cultures only interact with the larger society. The Anglo-Saxon culture (White Anglo-Saxon and Protestant) is an example of the multicultural model.

On the fusion model, there are interaction and mutual learning. Mixtures occur, which will produce a new culture with internal diversity. The Brazilian culture and the conceptualization of Freyre (1986; Rudmin, Wang and Castro, 2016) are examples of the fusion model. On the current article, the reference to Freyre is restricted to his greatest work *The masters and the slaves: A study in the development of Brazilian civilization*. Freyre's Luso-tropical theory is set aside, because of its ideological ambiguity (Castelo, 1998; Castro, 2014a; Vala, Lopes and Lima, 2008). Freyre's work will be discussed further, when the research approaches intermarriage.

On the intercultural model at private and at individual levels the minority may change or maintain its culture, because of the laissez-faire point of view. At the public level, the minority is expected to adapt the majority culture, for instance, at educational and at workplace. However, at the institutional level, the interaction among cultures is reduced. The values of the French Republic are an example of the intercultural model, because the universal values are not expected to change by the minority cultural influence.

2. Research problem: lack of equivalence

This article belongs to a Ph.D. dissertation prepared by Castro (2014a and 2014b). Yet, the current article must be perceived as independent. The dissertation had two central goals: to contextualize and to explore the Portuguese culture regarding the acculturation topic. The second goal was to approach acculturation as a reciprocal learning process (Rudmin, 2009). The dissertation applied the mixed method (Clark and Creswell, 2011), i.e., content analysis, ethnographic fieldwork in Metz, France, among Portuguese emigrants. The ethnographic fieldwork was also applied in Porto, Portugal, among Cape Verdean immigrants. Psychometric work was also used in the doctoral dissertation. Methodological

obstacles became visible on the literature review about the Portuguese emigration, because the research has established a comparison regarding the Anglo-Saxon culture. On the Anglo-Saxon literature, the pervasive approach is the Berry Model (2001) which main concern is the maintenance of the minority culture. On the Portuguese literature, in turn, the word multicultural is applied, but its variables are not applied (especially the cultural maintenance). Furthermore, the word assimilation is rarely employed. However, its variables are applied. For example, in Portugal, the word integration points out more to cultural adaptation than to cultural maintenance. Yet, on the Berry Model (2001) the word integration means learning the majority culture, and the maintenance of the minority culture. Therefore, the difference among conceptual meanings and methodological approaches caused problems.

In addition, the Portuguese literature about emigration is influenced by the French literature (Baganha, Góis and Pereira, 2005; Rocha-Trindade, 1970). There are French scholars who are writing about the Portuguese emigration, and even about its effects in Portugal (Charbit et al., 1997). The differences among the conceptual meanings posed problems about what the research was approaching, because the concepts can involve construct bias and, in particular lack, of equivalence (Ember and Ember, 2009). For instance, in Portugal, the word 'integration' can be understood as 'assimilation' rather than cultural maintenance of the multicultural model (Berry, 2001). The problem with the meanings and the different approaches boosted, because assimilation seemed to be the dominant model in the Portuguese literature about emigration (Oliveira, 2012). However, in the United States of America, the word 'assimilation' is still employed (Scott, 2009). On the Portuguese culture, it was very uncommon to find works whose titles or keywords were pointing out to the word 'assimilation' (Pereira and Tavares, 2000). In turn, in France, the word 'assimilation' was replaced by the word 'integration' (Safi, 2012), but the change reflected a historical guilty over the colonial period and not a theoretical change.

The word 'integration' is pointing out to a process in which the characteristics of immigrants will converge to the average French culture, and not to their cultural maintenance.

3. Brief historical description of the Portuguese emigration

3.1. The precursor phase

Godinho (1978) wrote that the Portuguese emigration phenomenon was structural. Some of the most prominent Portuguese novelists were writing about it (Namora, 1981). Three of the most acclaimed Portuguese novelists were emigrants; Castro (1982), Morais, (1904), and Torga (1943). Baganha, Góis and Pereira (2005) divided the emigration literature into three historical periods. And they have a precursor phase, which starts with the ‘Portuguese Discoveries’ (Serrão, 1970).

The perplexity about what is emigration and colonization is still present on the emigration literature, because both events occurred at the same time. The colonial empire lasted until the democratic revolution of 1974, and the Portuguese emigration started with the independence of Brazil in 1822. In addition, emigration and colonial empire are still important to understand the historical legacy (Castelo, 1998), the reactions regarding acculturation and also to understand immigration, because the latter increased with the decolonization process (Brettell, 2006). On the *Observatório da Emigração*’s database, the references related to the colonial past obtained 4.1% of the works. The ‘host’ countries were: Brazil, South Africa, Argentina and even the city of Malacca (Sarkissian, 2000).

3.2. The intercontinental phase and Brazil

The first phase is called intercontinental and began in 1822, because Brazil became independent. Brazil was also the largest destination for Portuguese emigrants (Baganha Góis and Pereira, 2005). The Portuguese emigration flow to Brazil only decreased on the mid-1950.

According to Brettell (1991), Castro (2008 and 2011), Martins (1956) and Serrão (1982), the Portuguese emigration to Brazil was not perceived as a fundamental cultural change. According to Rocha-Trindade and Fiori (2009) and Demartini (2010), the Portuguese

culture was favored, due to the common cultural background. However, Ribeiro (1994) and Silva (2013) reported the opposite.

During the intercontinental phase, nearly two millions of Portuguese emigrants went to Brazil (Baganha, Góis and Pereira, 2005) and this phase is still receiving the attention of scholars (Maia, 2007). According to the review, Brazil appeared with the highest number of publications, i.e., 24.4% in the period between 2001 and 2012. Furthermore, it should be noticed that nowadays there is a new emigration flow to Brazil.

3.3. The continental phase and France

The second phase is called continental, because France and, in a lesser extent, Germany were the main destinations (Baganha, 1998; Volovitch-Tavares, 2002). This phase began in the mid-50s and finished in the 70s. During this period nearly two millions of emigrants left Portugal (Arroteia, 1983). Therefore, this phase reached roughly the same number of emigrants than the first phase. However, the continental phase occurred in a shorter period of time.

3.4. The “decline” phase and the European Union

The third phase goes from the mid-80s of the 20th century until ‘today’ (Baganha, Góis and Pereira, 2005). Europe remained the main destination. In 1997, Baganha and Peixoto wrote that the emigration flow persisted, even if it was reduced. However, it should be noticed that the present financial and political crisis has generated a new flow. Consequently, there is a new emigration phase (Marques, 2009), which will be approached by the researchers. Brazil, Angola, Macau in China (Pessoa, 2010), Mozambique (Matos, 2009) and United Kingdom (Almeida and David, 2010) are some of the recent destinations.

4. Statistical analysis and article goals

Castro’s research (2014a and 2014b) employed secondary sources (Ember and Ember, 2009) in addition to primary sources. The most important secondary statistical source was *Observatório da Emigração*’s database. The thematic analysis on statistical databases aimed to get a clearer understanding of the appraisals regarding cultural changes. It also

aimed to clarify and to classify the emigration literature according to the acculturation models, updating that literature.

In March of 2012, the *Observatório da Emigração's* database had available 1025 references. The database was computed by four codes on SPSS: the themes of the publication, the year of publication, the language on which the works were written, and finally the 'host' country. The categorization of the works was taking into account titles, abstracts, keywords. Finally, the author of this article knew previously most of the works. The categorization carried out by Candeias et al. (2014) was performed by the following codes: 1) themes, 2) keywords, 3) host country, 4) historical period, 5) abstracts. Other important bibliographic sources about the emigration phenomenon are the works of Rocha-Trindade and Arroteia (1984), and Baganha and Góis (1999).

4.1. Theme of publication

The code theme is divided into 15 options: none or general (37.3%), because often the theme did not appear on the reference. The economic theme, political, socio-demographic, social networks (social networks, cultural associations, and marriage are together in this code) and return. Other themes were: transnational, ethnic identity, colonization, acculturation, education or social mobility and cultural maintenance. And still the themes gender, language, health and finally material acculturation.

The code theme was crossed with the year of the publication and with the 'host' countries codes. The research found out the following 'host' countries: France, Brazil, United States, among others. The presence of two or more countries on the same work was also encoded. The Anglo-Saxon acculturation literature has three main topics: coping (health), learning and ethnic identity. On the current literature review, the themes education, social mobility, and cultural maintenance are close to the multicultural approach. However, that theme only got 3.2% of the references. Most of the references were recent and they were published between 2001 and 2012 and were written in English. The theme health just got 1.6% of the references.

The themes of the assimilation model are Identity, Political, Socio-demographic, and Return. The theme Identity obtained 10.5% of the references and this is related to general concerns about the Portuguese identity. However, this theme is not concerned about the maintenance of the Portuguese culture, but rather with the sociocultural ‘integration’. The theme Political got 10% of the works. The theme Socio-demographic got 10% and the theme Return got 7% of the references. Those themes had often France as the ‘host’ country. In short, assimilation is the dominant model in the Portuguese literature about emigration.

4.2. Year of publication and host countries

The year of publication was divided from zero until 1974, from 1975 until 1985, from 1986 until 1991, from 1992 until 2000, and finally from 2001 until 2012. The code language entails Portuguese (56.8%), English (24.7%), French (14%) and Castilian (4.5%). On the database, almost all works were recent (55%), published between 2001 and 2012. There were only 1.5% of works published until 1974, 10.4% between 1975 and 1985, 11.7% between 1986 and 1991. And there were 21.4% of the references between 1992 and 2000. The ‘host’ country was another code employed in the statistical analysis. France was the most frequent ‘host’ country with 27% of the references and was the pervasive country on the references between 1975 and 1985, and between 1986 and 1991. The results were consistent with the continental phase. Until 1974, France and Brazil shared the same percentages of works, i.e., 40%, Canada obtained 20%. Overall, Brazil had 21.8%, and it was the second country with more references. The third country with more references was the United States with 15.9%. Canada got 9.6% of the references.

4.3. Acculturative appraisals on the Portuguese emigration literature

According to Brettell (1991), the appraisals about the Portuguese emigration began in the 17th century, because Duarte Ribeiro de Macedo (1618-1680) established a relationship between immigration and economy. Throughout the 19th century, intellectuals established diverse appraisals about emigration. On the last decades of the 19th century, Queirós (1979) wrote positively about the foreign influences. Herculano (1838 and 1879), by mid-century also wrote a positive appraisal about emigration. However, a few decades later, he

evaluates it negatively, due to economic reasons. The appraisal of Martins (1956 and 1978) was related to the lack of development and social inequalities.

The economic variable can be perceived as a decision utility between costs and benefits (Rudmin, 2009) regarding the individual emigration. The economic appraisal has multiple sources and different explanations (Serrão, 1982), i.e., lack of rural (Herculano, 1879; Monteiro, 1985) and industrial developments (Martins, 1956 and 1978), the Marxist and the push and pull explanations (Pires, 2003). The economic justification appears related to concerns about Portugal and the Portuguese position in the international arena. Besides being a cause, economy can also be an effect (Castro, 2011), according to Baganha, Góis and Pereira (2005), in the 80s emigration of the 20th century, literature reported concerns regarding the impact of emigration on the Portuguese economy and society. The economy theme obtained 1.9% of the outcomes.

The political theme is related to the economic topic and was emphasized by Brettell (1991) or by Monteiro (1985), because the political situation was a constraint to economic development, to social justice, and to freedom of movement (Baganha, 2005). Political situation can influence emigration (Bourhis at al., 1997), but emigration can also be perceived as a condition for political change. The political theme obtained 10.2%.

The socio-demographic references can be related to political and economic concerns and can be also approached as a cause and as an effect. For example, the increasing human desertification and asymmetrical relationships among Portugal and the host countries (Castro, 2008 and 2011; Castro and Marques, 2003) have a recursive causality. The socio-demographic studies are especially useful to contextualize acculturation, because some of the variables are successfully applied on the assimilation model, for example, intermarriage, low socioeconomic status or residential concentration (Scott, 2009). The socio-demographic variable obtained 9.7% of the works.

It is important to notice that intermarriage is also an important variable for the fusion model

(Freyre, 1986; Simons, 1901). According to Freyre (1986), the biological mixtures among the European males and the indigenous and the African females would lead to a social harmony. However, it is important to notice that the process was antagonistic, asymmetric and implied discrimination among genders and races. Intermarriage also reveals the limits of the multicultural model, because marriage implies a change in the phenotypes features and not their maintenance (the latter characteristic is the defining dimension of the multicultural model).

As Rudmin, Wang and Castro (2016) pointed out, biculturalism is impossible to achieve when two cultural characteristics are mutually exclusive. For example, it is impossible to be Jew and Christian at the same time, because both religions are monotheistic. According to Castro (2015), multiculturalism is also limited, because intercultural contact entails cultural change and it does not entail the full maintenance of the original culture. As Touraine (2007, p. 153) wrote: “The absolute multiculturalist hypothesis is as absurd as that of the cultural homogeneity of a city or country. Intercultural relations are the only reality - and they are what need to be studied, from trampling over the other to cultural mixing.”

The importance of intermarriage is not confined to the biological variable, because it also involves learning a second culture. Enculturation and acculturation are mixed, and intermarriage is related with fusion. Yet, usually, intermarriage is a variable of the assimilation model, since the majority tends to absorb the minority.

An interesting theme is the social networks, because they are important to obtain information and for social support. The social network is a relational theme, which refers to the processes of socialization and enculturation. Family networks play an important role in the immigration decision (Leandro, 2004). In addition to utility decision, social networks are also important to learn a second culture (Arends-Tóth and Van de Vijver, 2006), and still to maintain the cultural legacy (Poinard and Hily, 1983). For example, in France the activities of the Portuguese community were adapted to the French culture, implying to learn and to reinterpret the Portuguese culture (Cordeiro and Hily, 2000). Finally, the

acculturation of Portuguese emigrants can influence the Portuguese culture. The social networks theme obtained 3.2% of the works.

The return is an important theme. Immigration is defined by the United Nations as being temporary (Bilborrow et al., 1997; United Nations, 2002). When it takes less than one year is called of short-term. The word long-term is employed for a period longer than one year. The return theme is approached in the literature, since the departure of the Portuguese to Brazil (Castro, 2011 and 2012). On the continental emigration, the periodic return to Portugal without the expectation of the last return was approached as a problem (Brettell, 1979). Yet, the Portuguese emigrants were reporting a transnational or fusion culture. The appraisal about emigration often was not related to the cultural maintenance (characteristic of the multicultural model), but it was related to the alleged lack of socio-cultural adaptation regarding the French society. Yet, the Portuguese emigrants perceived low levels of discrimination (Pereira, 2012). The appraisal was not also placed on cultural mixtures (a feature of the fusion model), and on the likely influence of emigrants on the Portuguese and French cultures. And when the cultural mixtures were visible on the Portuguese landscape, the appraisal about them was negative (Castro, 2008, 2011, and 2012; Gonçalves, 1996). It happened, for example, with the construction of the 'French house'.

On the assimilation model, the return was perceived as a double migration, because it is presumed to require a new adaptation regarding the original culture, a requirement that increases for the second generations (Neto, 1997). Thus, the return was not approached as learning, but rather as something that menaced mental health. Thus, the immigration paradox is extended to the contact with the original culture, because learning a second culture is considered the best option, but, at the same time, it is perceived as a problem (Rudmin, 2009). The theme return obtained 7.4% of the references.

5. The bicultural individual as a problem

According to the statistical analysis, the dominant model is the assimilation and its themes. The multicultural cultural maintenance is not the main concern, but rather the socio-cultural

adaptation of the assimilation model. Another fact is that the acculturation concept was and it is still targeted by the appraisals of other cultures, including Lusophone cultures by Gilberto Freyre. The impact of emigrants was perceived often as a threat to the Portuguese culture. Emigration reveals the Portuguese internal problems, and also because of negative appraisals about the cultural change. In turn, the impact of Portuguese emigrants in the French culture was rarely approached. Therefore, on the literature about the Portuguese emigration the acculturation process has only one direction, regardless the Luso-tropical consensus ideology present in the Portuguese culture (Almeida, 2004). In Brazil, the Portuguese ruler group was reported to learn with the dominated cultures (Freyre, 1986; Rudmin, Wang and Castro, 2016) and the same happened in Japan (Castro, 2016a). Therefore, the acculturation phenomenon can be approached by the fusion model and as a dynamic process (Castro, 2015).

According to the assimilation model (Park, 1928), to share cultural traits is perceived as a problem. It is revealing that acculturation, more than learning, is approached as a socio-cultural problem. According to Park (1928), the immigrant person may be a 'marginal', because he or she does not have a relationship with the original culture and with the new culture. On the multicultural model, marginalization was also conceptualized by Berry (2001) as a minority attitude, because immigrants choose to forget both cultures. However, the common sense says that to abandon or to forget both cultures is not possible (Bourhis et al., 1997). Learning a second culture does not imply to unlearn the cultural legacy (Castro, 2016b). Consequently, the problem must be placed on the ethnic identity topic.

LaFromboise, Coleman and Gerton (1998) called 'acculturation' when an individual was acculturated, but was not accepted by the majority. Therefore, the problem is visible at sociological level, which requires the acceptance of the dominant cultural group (Teske and Nelson, 1974). The problem is not placed on acculturation, i.e., on learning (Castro, 2015 and 2016b; Rudmin, 2009). Acculturation is a matter of learning, rather than discrimination (Rudmin, 2009). On the Rudmin Model (2009), acculturation is defined as learning a second culture, although it is shaped by strong motivations. On the Rudmin Model (2009) discrimination and socio-economic status are control variables. Afterwards, LaFromboise,

Coleman and Gerton (1998) and Bourhis et al. (1997) approached the “marginal person” as “normal”, and not as a deviant person.

The migration phenomenon was defined by the United Nations (2002) as being temporary (Bilsborrow, et al., 1997). However, during the 80s of last century, it was generally agreed that a good number of the Portuguese continental emigrants would not return to Portugal (Brettell, 1979; Monteiro, 1994). The non-return had a geographic effect, i.e., the coming-back movement between France and Portugal (Charbit et al., 1997). In France, the Portuguese community was considered as well integrated and they perceived low levels of discrimination (Pereira, 2012).

The Portuguese community was returning periodically to Portugal. The circular movement among Portugal and the host countries was appraised negatively, because it was considered as dangerous to mental health (Neto, 2010). However, the Portuguese community was maintaining the Portuguese culture and it was reporting cultural mixtures. In addition, in France, the Portuguese emigrants are labeled themselves as sharing two cultures (bicultural) and this culture of mixtures was perceived as a problem (Hily and Oriol, 1993). Thus, the Portuguese emigrants produced a contradiction regarding the assimilation model, because they reported themselves as “integrated”, but they maintained their own identity and reported cultural mixtures (Charbit and Hily, 1997; Villanova, 2006). Therefore, the social ‘reality’ is going beyond the assimilation model, and it is going also beyond the multicultural model, even because it is not an institutional ‘reality’ in France. The bicultural identity can be perceived as fusion, because it involves changes and cultural mixtures (Rudmin, et al., 2016).

Consequently, the Portuguese emigration literature applied mainly the assimilation model and its variables. And the situation of the Portuguese emigrants rarely was approached by the multicultural model. Yet, the transnational approach (Bhatia, 2007) changed this point of view, and some main authors have changed their approaches (Baganha, Góis and Pereira, 2005; Leandro, 2003; Rocha-Trindade, 2008).

The transnational literature appears as a synonym of mixtures. In short, Park (1928) defined the “marginal man” as not belonging to any place (on diaspora). This it is not the case of the Portuguese emigrants, but rather the opposite: many of the Portuguese emigrants are moving and are living between two spaces, they have double residence (Villanova, 2006), double enculturation and, at least, two cultures.

6. Concluding remarks and suggestions

Under the light of the literature review outcomes, no acculturation model fits completely on the Portuguese emigrant ‘reality’. The Portuguese emigration is extended in time and in space, making generalizations hard to draw. There are variations according to age, generation, gender, education, socioeconomic status, perception of discrimination. In the literature review, it is clear that the assimilation model is dominant. The multicultural and the fusion models are sparse. Nevertheless, the fusion model is applied by the transnational analysis.

The acculturation process of the continental Portuguese migrants can be perceived as a case of fusion. Acculturation occurs on learning a second culture, but also on learning and on reformulating the Portuguese culture. During the acculturation process, cultural change can occur at the same time than maintenance. The result is a culture of mixtures, which is in a dynamic balance between change and maintenance.

Future researches should shift the acculturation research from an expected outcome on future (assimilation), and from an ideology (multicultural) to a dynamic approach, providing emphasis to learning and motivations. Researches should also be contextualized for Portuguese culture, taking into account the fusion model, which was conceptualized by Freyre or by the transnational analysis. Researchers should take into account the gains and losses of cultural groups, because acculturation is an antagonistic phenomenon and it is often asymmetric. It is also important to consider which cultural group is passive and active in the acculturation process.

The multicultural model should be also taken into account, in to approach the Portuguese cultural maintenance. Emigrants reinterpret and change the Portuguese and the host cultures. The outcomes of the literature review report that acculturation, despite having unique heuristics qualities has been dismissed, but the outcomes also report that the emigration literature has followed the historical development of the acculturation concept. The emphasis on the assimilation model points out to its colonial and to its ethnocentric origins. However, the emergence of the multicultural model and, above all, the transnational approach reveals that the Portuguese emigration literature is today closer to the earlier acculturation definitions proposed by Powell (1880), Simons (1901), and Redfield, Linton and Herskovits (1936).

In conclusion, on the current article acculturation is thought to be contextualized, because the cultural backgrounds shape the reactions regarding the acculturative changes. The cultural backgrounds also shape the theoretical formulations. Therefore, acculturation needs to be contextualized and the Portuguese literature needs to be updated.

References

Almeida, J. C. P. and David, C. (2010). Portuguese migrant workers in the UK: A case study of Thetford, Norfolk. In: *Portuguese Studies*. 26, pp. 27-40.

Almeida, M. V. (2004). *An earth-colored sea: "Race," culture, and the politics of identity in the postcolonial Portuguese-colored Sea*. Oxford: Berghahn Books.

Araújo, M. and Maeso, S. R. (2010). Explorando o eurocentrismo nos manuais portugueses de história. In: *Estudos de Sociologia*. 15, pp. 239-270.

Arends-Tóth, J. V. and Van de Vijver, F. J. R. (2006). Issues in conceptualization and assessment of acculturation. In: Bornstein, M. H. and Cote, L. R. (Eds.). *Acculturation and parent-child relationships: Measurement and development*. Mahwah, NJ: Erlbaum, pp. 33-62.

Arroteia, A. (1983). *A emigração portuguesa - Suas origens e distribuição*. Lisboa: Instituto de Cultura e Língua Portuguesa.

Baganha, M. I. (1998). Portuguese emigration after the First World War. In: Pinto, A. C. (Ed.). *Modern Portugal*. Palo Alto: Society for the Promotion of Science and Scholarship, pp. 189-205.

Baganha, M. I. (2005). Política de imigração: A regulação dos fluxos. In: *Revista Crítica de Ciências Sociais*. 73, pp. 29-44.

Baganha, M. I. and Góis, P. (1999). Migrações internacionais de e para Portugal. O que sabemos e para onde vamos? In: *Revista Crítica de Ciências Sociais*. 52-53, pp. 229-280.

Baganha, M. I. and Peixoto, J. (1997). Trends in the 90's: The Portuguese migratory experience. In: Baganha, M. (Ed.). *Immigration in Southern Europe*. Oeiras: Celta Editora, pp. 15-40.

Baganha, M. I., Góis, P. and Pereira, P. T. (2005). International migration from and to Portugal: What do we know and where are we going? In: Zimmermann, K. (Ed.). *European migration: What do we know?* Oxford: Oxford University Press, pp. 415-458.

Barth, F. (1969). *Ethnic groups and boundaries. The social organization of culture difference*. Oslo: Universitetsforlaget.

Berry, J. W. (2001). A psychology of immigration. In: *Journal of Social Issues*. 57, pp. 615-631.

Bhatia, S. (2007). Rethinking culture and identity in psychology: Towards a transnational cultural Psychology. In: *Journal of Theoretical and Philosophical Psychology*. 27, pp. 301-321.

Bilsborrow, R. E., Hugo, G., Oberai, A. S. and Zlotnik, H. (1997). *International Migration Statistics*. Geneva: International Labour Office.

Boas, F. (1982). *Race, language, and culture*. Chicago: University of Chicago Press.

Bourhis, R. Y., Moise, C. L., Perreault, S. and Senécal, S. (1997). Towards an interactive acculturation model: A social psychological approach. In: *International Journal of Psychology*. 32, pp. 369-386.

Brettell, C. (1979). Emigrar para voltar: A Portuguese ideology of return migration. In: *Papers in Anthropology*. 20, pp. 1-20.

Brettell, C. (1991). *Homens que partem mulheres que esperam: Consequências da emigração numa freguesia minhota*. Lisboa: Publicações Dom Quixote.

Brettell, C. (2006). Portugal's first post-Colonials: Citizenship, identity and the repatriation of Goans. In: *Portuguese Studies Review*. 14, pp. 143-170.

Candeias, P., Góis, P., Marques, J. C. and Peixoto J. (2014). *Emigração portuguesa: bibliografia comentada (1980-2013)*. Lisboa: ISEG - Instituto Superior de Economia e Gestão.

Castelo, C. S. (1998). *O modo português de estar no mundo: O luso-tropicalismo e a ideologia colonial portuguesa (1933-1961)*. Porto: Afrontamento.

Castro, F. (1982). *Emigrantes*. Lisboa: Guimarães Editora.

Castro, J. F. P. (2008). *Os efeitos da aculturação no vaivém da emigração continental: Um estudo de caso em Melgaço*. Master Dissertation. Porto: Universidade Fernando Pessoa.

Castro, J. F. P. (2011). Os efeitos da aculturação no vaivém da emigração continental: Um estudo de caso em Melgaço. In: *Revista Portuguesa de Estudos Regionais*. 25/26, pp. 67-76.

Castro, J. F. P. (2012). The Portuguese tile in the Rudmin Acculturation Learning Model: A fusion case. In: Gaiser L. and Čurčić, D. (Eds.). *EMUNI, bridging gaps in the Mediterranean research space. Conference proceedings of the 4th EMUNI Research Souk, 17-18 April*. El. Knjiga/Portorož: EMUNI University, pp. 618-625.

Castro, J. F. P. (2014a). *O contexto da aculturação português através do modelo de Rudmin: Do encontro intercultural com o Japão até ao Luso-Tropicalismo*. Doctoral Thesis. Porto: Universidade Fernando Pessoa.

Castro, J. F. P. (2014b). O contexto da aculturação português através do modelo de Rudmin: Do encontro intercultural com o Japão até ao Luso-Tropicalismo. In: Gabinete de Relações Internacionais e Apoio ao Desenvolvimento Institucional (Coord.). *Atas dos Dias da Investigação na UFP Research Days Proceedings*. Porto: Gabinete de Relações Internacionais e Apoio ao Desenvolvimento Institucional.

Castro, J. F. P. (2015). Towards a Psychology of fusion in the acculturation phenomenon. In: Gabinete de Relações Internacionais e Apoio ao Desenvolvimento Institucional (Coord.). *Atas dos Dias da Investigação na UFP Research Days Proceedings*. Porto: Gabinete de Relações Internacionais e Apoio ao Desenvolvimento Institucional.

Castro, J. F. P. (2016a). Acculturation in the Portuguese overseas experience with Japan: A Rudmin Model application. In: *Daxiyangguo: Revista Portuguesa de Estudos Asiáticos*. 20, 89-120.

Castro, J. F. P. (2016b). A aprendizagem numa segunda cultura e a identidade étnica dos indígenas brasileiros através numa rede social: estudo exploratório. In: *Religacion, Revista de Ciencias Sociales y Humanidades*. 2, 75-94.

Castro, J. F. P. and Marques, A. (2003). *Emigração e contrabando*. Melgaço: Centro Desportivo e Cultural de São Paio.

Charbit, Y., Hily, M. A., Poinard, M. and Petit, V. (1997). *Le va-et-vien identitaire : Migrants portugais et villages d'origine*. Paris: Presses Universitaires de France.

Clark, V. L. P. and Creswell, J. W. (2011). *Designing and conducting mixed methods research*. London: Sage Publications.

Cordeiro, A. and Hily, M. A. (2000). La fête des Portugais: Héritage et invention. In: *Revue Européenne de Migrations Internationales*. 16, pp. 59-76.

Demartini, Z. B. F. (2010). Imigrantes: Entre políticas, conflitos e preconceitos. In: *Cadernos CERU*. 21, pp. 49-75.

Ember, C. R. and Ember, M. (2009). *Cross-cultural research methods*. Lanham: AltaMira Press.

Feldman-Bianco, B. (2007). Empire, postcoloniality and diasporas: The Portuguese case. In: *Hispanic Research Journal*. 8, pp. 279-290.

Freyre, G. (1986). *The masters and the slaves: A study in the development of Brazilian civilization*. Berkeley: University of California Press.

Godinho, V. M. (1978). L'émigration portugaise (XV-XX siècles). Une constante structurale et les réponses aux changements du monde. In: *Revista de História Económica e Social*. 1, pp. 5-32.

Gonçalves, A. (1996). *Imagens e clivagens: Os residentes face aos emigrantes*. Porto: Edições Afrontamento.

Herculano, A. (1838). *A emigração para o Brazil. Opúsculos*. Vol. 2. Lisboa: Editorial Presença.

Herculano, A. (1879). *A emigração, I carta. Opúsculos*. Vol. 4. Lisboa: Viúva Bertrand.

Hily, M. A. and Oriol, M. (1993). Deuxième génération portugaise: La gestion des ressources identitaires. In: *Revue Européenne de Migrations Internationales*. 9, pp. 81-93.

LaFromboise, T., Coleman, H. L. K. and Gerton, J. (1998). Psychological impact of biculturalism: Evidence and theory. In: Organista, P. B., Chun, K. M. and Marín, G. (Eds). *Readings in ethnic psychology*. New York: Routledge, pp. 117-155.

Leal, J. (2011). The past is a foreign country? Acculturation theory and the anthropology of globalization. In: *Etnográfica*. 15, pp. 313-336.

Leandro, M. E. (2003). Les nouvelles générations sociales de jeunes Portugais en Allemagne et en France. In: *Recherches en Anthropologie au Portugal*. 9, pp. 61-77.

Leandro, M. E. (2004). Dinâmica social familiar dos projectos migratórios: Uma perspectiva analítica. In: *Análise Social*. 39, pp. 93-118.

Maia, F. P. S. (2007). A emigração para o Brasil no discurso parlamentar oitocentista. In: *População e Sociedade*. 14, pp. 51-68.

Malinowski, B. (1958). *The dynamics of cultural change: An inquiry into race relations in Africa*. New Haven: Yale University Press.

Marques, J. C. (2009). E continuam a partir: As migrações portuguesas contemporâneas. In: *Ler História*. 56, pp. 27-44.

Martins, O. (1956). *Fomento rural e emigração: Obras completas*. Lisboa: Guimarães Editores.

Martins, O. (1978). *O Brasil e as colónias portuguesas*. Lisboa: Guimarães Editores.

Matos, E. D. (2009). Post-colonial Portuguese migration to Mozambique: An examination of causes, effects and future implications for development. In: *International Migration*. 47, pp. 157-184.

Monteiro, P. F. (1985). *Terra que já foi terra: Análise sociológica de nove lugares agro-pastoris da serra da Lousã*. Lisboa: Edições Salamandra.

Monteiro, P. F. (1994). *Emigração: O eterno mito do retorno*. Oeiras: Celta Editora.

Morais, W. (1904). *Cartas do Japão*. Porto: Livraria Magalhães e Moniz.

Namora, F. (1981). Uma avaria no automóvel. In: *Cidade solitária: Narrativas*. Amadora: Livraria Bertrand, pp. 189-200.

Neto, F. (1997). Estudos de psicologia intercultural: Nós e os outros. Lisboa: Fundação Calouste Gulbenkian.

Neto, F. (2010). Re-acculturation attitudes among adolescents from returned Portuguese immigrant families. In: *International Journal of Intercultural Relations*. 34, pp. 221-232.

Observatório da Emigração [Em linha]. Disponível em <http://observatorioemigracao.pt>. [Consultado em 01/03/2012].

Oliveira, N. F. C. (2012). *Políticas de categorização étnica, Portugal e o Brasil em perspectiva comparada*. Doctoral Thesis. Lisboa: ISCTE-IUL.

Park, R. E. (1928). Human migration and the marginal man. In: *The American Journal of Sociology*. 33, pp. 881-893.

Pereira, P. T. and Tavares, L. P. (2000). Is schooling of migrants' children more like that of their parents, their cousins, or their neighbors? In: *Journal of International Migrations and Integration*. I, pp. 443-459.

Pereira, V. (2012). Os futebolistas invisíveis: Os portugueses em França e o futebol. In: *Etnográfica*. 16, pp. 97-115.

Pessoa, I. (2010). Cosmopolitan Portuguese youth: The world as home after the Macao migratory experience. In Cairns, D. (Org.). *Youth on the move. European youth and geographical mobility*. Morlenbach: VS Verlag, pp. 23-34.

Pires, R. (2003). *Migrações e integração: Teoria e aplicações à sociedade portuguesa*. Oeiras: Celta Editora.

Poinard, M. and Hily, M. A. (1983). Réseaux informels et officiels dans la communauté portugaise en France. In: *Espace, populations, societies*. 2, pp. 57-68.

Powell, J. W. (1880). *Introduction to the study of Indian languages: With words phrases and sentences to be collected*. Washington: Government Printing Office.

Queirós, E. (1979). *A emigração como força civilizadora*. Lisboa: Perspectivas e Realidades.

Redfield, R., Linton, R. and Herskovits, M. T. (1936). Memorandum for the study of acculturation. In: *American Anthropologist*. 38, pp. 149-152.

Ribeiro, G. S. (1994). «Por que você veio encher o pandulho aqui?». Os portugueses, o antilusitanismo e a exploração das moradias populares no Rio de Janeiro da República Velha. In: *Análise Social*. 127, pp. 31-54.

Rocha-Trindade, M. B. (1970). *Observation psycho-sociologique d'un groupe de Portugais dans la banlieue Parisienne (Orsay)*. Paris: Faculté des Lettres et des Sciences Humaines de Paris.

Rocha-Trindade, M. B. (2008). Problemas das migrações contemporâneas em Portugal. In: *Cadernos Ceru*. 19, pp. 81-97.

Rocha-Trindade, M. B. and Arroiteia, J. (1984). *Bibliografia da emigração portuguesa*. Lisboa: Instituto de Português de Ensino à Distância.

Rocha-Trindade, M. B. and Fiori, N. (2009). Migrações entre Portugal e Brasil: Reciprocidade de preferências 1908-1945. In: *Migrações*. 5, pp. 203-219.

Rudmin, F. W. (2009). Constructs, measurements and models of acculturation and acculturative stress. In: *International Journal of Intercultural Relations*. 33, pp. 106-123.

Rudmin, F. W., Wang, B. and Castro, J. F. P. (2016). Acculturation research critiques and alternative research designs. In: Schwartz, S. J. and Unger, J. B. (Ed.). *Handbook of Acculturation and Health*. Oxford: Oxford University Press.

Safi, M. (2012). Penser l'intégration des immigrants: Les enseignements de la sociologie américaine. In: *Sociologie*. 2, pp. 149-164.

Sarkissian, M. (2000). *D'Albuquerque's children: Performing tradition in Malaysia's Portuguese settlement*. Chicago: The University of Chicago Press.

Scott, D. M. (2009). Portuguese Americans' acculturation, socioeconomic integration, and amalgamation. How far have they advanced? In: *Sociologia, Problemas e Práticas*. 61, pp. 41-64.

Serrão, J. (1970). Conspecto histórico da emigração à portuguesa. In: *Análise Social*. 8, pp. 597-617.

Serrão, J. (1982). *Temas oitocentistas: Para a história de Portugal no século passado*. Vol. 1. Lisboa: Livros Horizonte.

Silva, I. C. (2013). *Espelho fraterno: o Brasil e o republicanismo português a transição para o século XX*. Lisboa: Divina Comédia.

Simons, S. E. (1901). Social assimilation. I. In: *American Journal of Sociology*. 6, pp. 790-822.

Taylor, C. (2012). Interculturalism or multiculturalism? In: *Philosophy & Social Criticism*. 38, pp. 413-423.

Teske, R. H. C. and Nelson, B. H. (1974). Acculturation and assimilation: A clarification. In: *American Ethnologist*. 1, pp. 351-367.

Torga, M. (1943). *O senhor Ventura*. Coimbra: Atlântida.

Touraine, A. (2007). *A new paradigm for understanding today's world*. Cambridge, UK: Polity Press.

United Nations (2002). *International Migration Report 2002*. New York: United Nations.

Vala, J., Lopes, D. and Lima, M. (2008). Black immigrants in Portugal: Luso-Tropicalism and prejudice. In: *Journal of Social Issues*. 64, pp. 287-302.

Villanova, R. (2006). Double residence: A space for intergenerational relations. Portuguese immigrants in France in the twentieth and twenty-first centuries. In: *Portuguese Studies Review*. 14, pp. 241-261.

Volovitch-Tavares, M-C. (2002). Les Portugais des trente glorieuses. In: *Plein droit*. 55, pp. 3-6.